

LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL ADAPTATION IN MULTILINGUAL CLASSROOMS**Mirkabil Alimbaev Anvarovich**

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mirkabil.alimbaev@gmail.com<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17512260>**Abstract**

This article examines the instructional and cultural challenges faced by novice teachers in multilingual classrooms, with a focus on language scaffolding and culturally responsive teaching. Drawing from theoretical frameworks such as Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development and Culturally Relevant Pedagogy, it highlights the necessity of equipping novice educators with practical tools and training in scaffolding techniques, including teacher talk, problem-based learning (PBL), and digital scaffolding. The paper also explores how cultural responsiveness, student-centered pedagogy, and multicultural curriculum development are critical for fostering inclusive learning environments. The review underscores that without sufficient preparation in cultural sensitivity and instructional adaptability, novice teachers may struggle to meet the linguistic and socio-cultural needs of their students. It concludes by recommending targeted professional development and pre-service training to enhance teacher readiness for diverse classrooms.

Keywords: language scaffolding, culturally responsive teaching, multilingual classrooms, novice teachers, teacher professional development

Language Scaffolding and Instructional Strategies

Language scaffolding is a key instructional strategy which every novice teacher should embrace when teaching in multilingual classrooms especially where language learning is a challenge. Scaffolding involves the process of defining the learning tasks into smaller parts and then gradually transferring the responsibility of the task back to the student. This approach is particularly useful for ELLs as it allows them to develop language skills in the context where these skills are modeled and reinforced. Some of the techniques that may be included are use of simpler language, providing pictures to complement words, engaging the students' prior knowledge and incorporating gestures or demonstrations. Chandran et al. (2022) state that such strategies allow students to participate in the language learning process in a more meaningful manner, which is important for the development of language and thought.

However, novice teachers in multilingual and multicultural environment may not know how to use the right scaffolding strategies because of inexperience and lack of training. Liu (2014) pointed out that most new teachers do not possess the ability to use these techniques in a way that would be suitable for the language and cultural diversity of the students. Language simplification or the use of visual aids for reinforcement calls for an understanding of the language and cultural background of the students which many new entry teachers may not have attained. Liu also pointed out that novice teachers may feel overwhelmed by the challenge of addressing the needs of all the learners, which results in an uneven use of scaffolding and consequently, reduces its positive impact on language issues.

A review of literature by Gibbons (2002) on language scaffolding in multilingual classrooms shows that scaffolding is only effective if the teachers are able to challenge the learners and at the same time support them. According to Gibbons, scaffolding should be 'high challenge-high support', that is, the tasks should be intellectually demanding but can be done

with the help of the teacher. It is, therefore, difficult for novice teachers to mediate this balance since they either offer a high level of support and thus minimize students' participation or offer low levels of support and thus maximize students' frustration. The current work reveals the importance of the training that can aid novice teachers to identify when and how they should modify their scaffolding approach to accommodate the dynamic needs of the students.

Zhukova (2017) uses problem-based learning (PBL) as a way of teaching through language scaffolding to show how novice teachers can employ this method to enhance language learning while interacting with the students. PBL is a learning model where students are given problems that simulate real-life situations and learn through solving those problems in groups therefore promoting language use. According to Zhukova's findings, PBL is an extremely powerful approach for language learning since it forces students to communicate and, thus, use language purposefully. Nevertheless, this approach presupposes good counseling skills and profound knowledge of language needs of the learners, and it may be beyond the capabilities of novice teachers. Without such skills, the novice teachers may not be able to steer the discussion properly and this may lead to poor language development with instances of misconstructions. Professional development in PBL strategies can enable the novice teachers to acquire the necessary skills to implement this approach effectively hence enabling the students to engage in more meaningful language learning.

According to Stanley and Stevenson (2017), another area that novices struggle with is the management of 'teacher talk'. Teacher talk can be defined as the language and instructional talk that teachers use in order to facilitate, teach and communicate with the students. In multilingual classrooms, teacher talk is crucial for comprehension since ELLs require explicit, simple, and orderly language to get messages and instructions. Stanley and Stevenson noted that the new teachers had a difficult time with the aspect of language control whereby the language that they used was often complex and thus provided instructions that were difficult to follow and may have been delivered too quickly for the ELLs to catch. Improper strategies of teacher talk can thus become a barrier in communication whereby the students are unable to understand the content that is being presented as well as being able to interact with others. Therefore, novice teachers need to be trained on how to adapt their language, how to chunk the information and use language models, elaborations, and gestures to help the students understand.

The idea of scaffolding in language learning is consistent with Vygotsky's (1978) theory of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) which postulates that a learner can achieve more with the help of a more knowledgeable person. In language learning, scaffolding is the help given to the ELLs in the form of support which is gradually reduced as the ELLs become more comfortable with the target language. However, these beginning teachers may have difficulty with this, they may take off support at the wrong time or they may hold on to it for too long which will only slow the students down. Vygotsky's theory underlines the importance of the training that would help teachers determine when the students are prepared to work more independently, to help beginning teachers in determining when and how to scaffold.

August and Shanahan (2006) discuss ways by which language scaffolding can be improved for ELLs, including the need to connect content and language objectives when planning lessons. They suggest that language and content ought to be integrated in that language scaffolding techniques should be incorporated in the subject matter. As such, this approach entails that the novice teacher has to understand how to teach language and content at the same time which

may be difficult if the teacher has not undergone specific training. According to August and Shanahan, content-specific language scaffolding does not only help in the acquisition of language but also enhances cognitive engagement whereby the ELLs are able to engage in lessons without being limited by language barriers. Helping novice teachers to understand how to state language objectives that are consistent with content objectives can improve their ability to teach language to students.

Besides the traditional scaffolding techniques, digital tools present new ways of scaffolding language in multilingual classrooms. According to Chiu (2021), the language scaffolding with technology, for instance using applications, software, and on-line tools, can help the novice teachers in delivering multimedia based lessons. Chiu's research shows that digital scaffolding tools can help the novice teachers by providing the student with visual and audio cues to break down language and content barriers. However, these tools if misused or used in the wrong manner can create confusion and information overload in the students. Through this, novice teachers will be able to learn how to incorporate the use of digital scaffolding tools in their teaching thus increasing the number of strategies they can use to teach language to the multilingual students.

Cultural Responsiveness and Student-Centered Teaching

Culturally responsive teaching is a teaching approach that demands the teachers appreciate and include students' culture and language in the learning process. This approach is based on the sociocultural theory which states that learning is contextual and is a product of the culture and social context that surrounds it. Kourieos and Diakou (2019) state that culturally responsive teaching not only includes the process of acknowledging students' identities but also improves motivation by linking the material to students' experiences. This approach makes the teachers understand that the backgrounds of the students are a plus rather than a drawback, thus creating a culture that accepts diversity in the classroom. However, beginner teachers have difficulties in integrating Culturally Responsive, Student-Centered Teaching Practices into their practice because of the lack of cultural knowledge and experience as well as the lack of training in this area.

To novices, dealing with the cultural differences of the students can be difficult as it involves understanding and application. Alhamad (2018) emphasizes on the need to be culturally sensitive in countries for instance Saudi Arabia where students' cultural beliefs, values, and expectations shape their learning process, social relations with the teacher and others. Alhamad noticed that many new teachers, who are not accustomed to the culture of the society in which they serve, have difficulty in communicating with the students, since their approach to teaching might be different from what the students are used to. New teachers may not be aware of certain cultural practices and therefore may use teaching strategies that are culturally insensitive and this may create a problem in the classroom. This therefore calls for pre-service and in-service training of teachers in cultural sensitivity and adaptability.

Likewise, in Vietnam, the study by Lap, Ngoc, and Thao in 2022 revealed that novice teachers who adopt culturally responsive teaching practices are more likely to establish good relationships with students especially in classrooms that are diverse in terms of language and culture. However, the study also reveals that many novice teachers in Vietnam perceive that they do not have the skills to alter their teaching practices in accordance with the needs of culturally diverse learners. This lack of preparation leads to inflexible approaches to teaching which may

involve the use of a single approach that is not suitable for all the learners. The authors of this study also pointed out that culturally responsive teaching is very effective in multilingual classrooms since it helps to appreciate and accommodate diversity in language while creating a culture of acceptance in the classroom.

Gay (2010), a well-known scholar in culturally responsive teaching, states that this approach is not just about recognizing the cultural differences but about embracing them in every aspect of learning process including curriculum, and classroom practices. According to Gay, culturally responsive teachers are those who are able to modify their teaching and learning materials, assessment and management practices to reflect the culture of the students. For these adaptations for novice teachers, it is important to understand the cultural contexts of the students which can be quite a challenging task due to the fact that the teachers may not have had much exposure to it. Culturally responsive teaching should be introduced in teacher preparation programs so that novice teachers are well prepared to teach students of diverse cultural background.

According to Banks and Banks (2016), culturally responsive pedagogy can be further understood with the help of multicultural education that calls for the integration of various voices and cultures in the curriculum. This approach is particularly crucial for the classrooms where students have different language and different culture. For a beginning teacher, it is difficult to come up with multicultural curriculum which depicts students' real-world experiences without being taught how to choose and modify the materials. According to Banks and Banks, teacher education programs should help novice teachers to understand how to design lesson plans that include students' culture and values. Thus, when teachers include a variety of people and their stories into the curriculum, the content becomes more meaningful and connected to students' worlds, which, in turn, improves students' engagement.

Ladson-Billings (1995) introduced Culturally Relevant Pedagogy which has the following features: It has identified three main aspects of culturally relevant pedagogy: academic achievement, cultural integrity and sociopolitical awareness. According to Ladson-Billings, it is not enough for teachers to help students to achieve academically but they should also help the students to develop cultural competence which is the ability to understand and appreciate one's own culture and that of others. It means that novice teachers have to understand the cultural identity of students. This approach can be especially effective in the multicultural environment because it makes students recognize that their cultural background can be a resource for learning. However, first-year teachers always complain that they are not very certain about how to go about cultural competence in the classroom and this hampers their efforts in creating an atmosphere of inclusion in the classroom.

Tajeddin and Bolouri (2023) pointed out that teachers must be trained on cultural sensitivity prior to joining the field, therefore teacher preparation programs should include lessons that help teachers to understand the difficulties and ways of teaching in multicultural and multilingual schools. This training should not only provide theoretical knowledge about cultural diversity but also the ways of modifying lessons, dealing with multicultural classes and solving cultural conflicts in class. According to Tajeddin and Bolouri's research, teachers who go through the training on cultural sensitivity are more likely to feel equipped to work in the multicultural and multilingual schools since they have the skills to alter their teaching according to the culture of the students.

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